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OPA tomography of non-Gaussian states of light

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Abstract

Current advances in nonlinear optics have made it possible to perform a homodyne-like tomography of an unknown state without highly efficient detectors or a strong local oscillator. Thereby, a new experimental direction has been opened into multimode and large-bandwidth quantum optics. An optical parametric amplifier (OPA) allows us to reconstruct the quadrature distribution of an unknown state directly from the measured intensity distribution with high precision. We propose adding a controllable displacement to the standard scheme, thus, obtaining a method applicable even to asymmetric and non-Gaussian states while significantly increasing estimation accuracy and lowering the OPA amplification requirement. To demonstrate the power of our method, we accurately detect the sub-Planck phase-space structure by obtaining distillable squeezing from the OPA estimates of various non-Gaussian states. With the improvements, OPA tomography became a generally applicable loss-tolerant and efficient alternative to homodyne detection.

1. Introduction

Homodyne detection is a well-established phase-sensitive technique in quantum optics and quantum technology to measure nonclassical [1, 2] and quantum non-Gaussian states of light [3]. Simultaneously, it is a basis for quantum tomography [4–7] capable of reconstructing the density matrix and its equivalents like the characteristic function [8, 9], and the Wigner function [10, 11]. This technique is based on highly efficient photodetection and a highly intensive local oscillator that filters only the signal modes that match it. Due to losses, the reconstructed states may miss Wigner negativity and quadrature squeezing [12, 13]. However, non-Gaussian states may still contain nonclassical sub-Planck structures in the phase space [14]. The sub-Planck structure can be operationally quantified using an amount of squeezing distillable from such non-Gaussian states [15, 16]. Many times, experimental setups in quantum optics, but also other fields using optical readout, like quantum optomechanics [17, 18], atomic ensemble experiments [19], and cavity quantum electrodynamics with atoms [20] have been limited by homodyne detection.

Using amplifiers to perform or enhance quantum measurements in optics is not a new concept starting with Caves' work from 1981 [21] proposing the 'squeezed state technique' to improve the accuracy of gravitational wave detection and Leonhardt [22] suggesting a preamplification step to improve homodyning in 1994; also, phase-insensitive amplification is an essential element of the all-optical quantum teleportation scheme proposed in [23] in 1999. Since then, phase-sensitive optical amplifiers have been extensively proposed and used to prepare and manipulate quantum non-Gaussian states [24, 25], protect them against decoherence [26, 27] and increase the efficiency of quantum interfaces and gates [28–30]. More recent examples include [31], which proposes a scheme for photon number resolving quantum non-demolition measurement based on phase-sensitive amplification and highlights the potential of OPAs in quantum computation, and [32], where it the combination of nonlinear amplifiers and noisy linear detectors was shown to achieve ideal measurements of the normal operator.

Recently, to achieve phase-sensitive terahertz-order detection bandwidth [33] and signal measurement in the spectral domain [34], adding parametric pre-amplification prior to homodyne detection [35–39] or intensity detection [40] has been experimentally tested. It has been proposed as a viable solution for realizing

all-optical quantum information processing with over-THz clock frequency [41], and high-dimensional quantum information applications [42, 43]. Parametric amplification has also been shown to be useful in improving the loss tolerance in an interferometric scheme [44]. Even though the limits of its performance in long-distance fiber communication have been studied [45], a systematic analysis and comparison of techniques exploiting parametric amplification to estimate quantum non-Gaussian states of light are missing, including possible techniques to lower the estimation error. Such quantum non-Gaussian states are essential resources for optical [46, 47], quantum communication [48, 49] and computing applications [50, 51].

In direct connection to the current work, Shaked and colleagues suggested in 2018 [37] parametric homodyning as a means to perform broadband homodyne measurements. By amplifying the input in a single direction, they were able to measure the spectrum of the light corresponding to the amplified quadrature. Taking the idea further in the state tomography direction, Kalash *et al* [40] estimated quadrature distributions using high-gain OPA solely from intensity measurements in a loss-tolerant scheme. Besides loss tolerance, the important feature of the setup is that it can work with multimode states due to the nature of parametric amplification [52, 53]. Their post-processing technique, however, can be refined and generalized to asymmetrical and compound distributions of non-Gaussian states, as we will explain and demonstrate in the current manuscript. Furthermore, we also explore how different types of noise limit the applicability of our approach and how amending the original measurement setup to include a displacement can improve estimation accuracy. We present two approaches to estimating asymmetric quadrature probability densities: a) using a single displacement large enough to ensure the positivity of the support of the quadrature distribution, and b) using multiple smaller displacements and a consequent minimization based on the observed histogram of intensities.

In this paper, we propose and apply a model of OPA tomography for quantum non-Gaussian states (including imperfections), and then describe our improvement and generalization. Then we give our results, which contain a detailed analysis of the improvement of estimation efficiency for squeezed states; we show high estimation quality for different non-Gaussian states, we compare the efficiencies of low-efficiency intensity and homodyne detectors and provide an efficient estimate of distillable squeezing [54, 55] from sub-Planck structures [14]. Finally, we draw the conclusions and provide an outlook on future development. The details of the proposed techniques, details of Fock state simulations, and the robustness analysis against different imperfections can be found in the appendix.

2. Methods

2.1. Model and main idea

In the following, we describe our model (see figure 1), which is based on the results in [40]. The task is to reconstruct the probability density function of a quadrature using low-efficiency intensity or homodyne detection and OPA pre-amplification without making assumptions on the initial state. In our simulations and analysis, we will use squeezed coherent states with and without displacement, classical non-Gaussian mixtures of two overlapping squeezed states, and quantum non-Gaussian Fock states as initial states.

The main idea behind the experimental approach is to compensate for detector inefficiency by amplifying the state in one direction using an OPA. After amplification, we measure either the intensity of the output state for multimode states, which will dominantly contain the amplified quadrature [40] or use low-efficiency and noisy homodyne detection for telecom-bandwidth experiments [33]. One can apply a phase shift prior to the amplification step in order to be able to measure quadratures along multiple directions in order to subsequently reconstruct the whole Wigner function. As the latter is a standard task [4–7], in the current work, we focus only on the quality of the reconstructed histogram along a single direction, which we denote by x .

2.2. OPA tomography based on intensity detection

Let us first look at the intensity-based scheme; the homodyne scheme is investigated in section 5.

In terms of annihilation and creation operators, we define the position quadrature as $X = (a^\dagger + a)/\sqrt{2}$, and the momentum quadrature as $P = (a - a^\dagger)/i\sqrt{2}$; $[X, P] = i$. The intensity-based scheme exploits that for sufficiently large values of the parametric gain G , one can approximate the output photocurrent by

$$i_{x^2} = \frac{1}{2} \left[\sqrt{\eta_{\text{out}}} (e^G X + d) + \varepsilon_{\text{out}} \right]^2 + \xi_{\text{det}}, \quad (1)$$

where we consider i_{x^2} to be already normalized to correspond to the number of photons. The main novelty of the scheme is the addition of displacement d . We consider the following post-amplification imperfections in our model of the scheme: an aggregated transmissivity η_{out} , an additive Gaussian quadrature noise ε_{out} with zero mean and standard deviation δ_{out} and a detector noise ξ_{det} as an independent Poissonian dark noise [56,

57]. In practice, the loss η_{out} mainly comes from optical filtering, while the noise can primarily be attributed to the detector's electronic noise ξ_{det} [40]. Note that the contribution from the momentum quadrature is neglected in (1) (due to the large gain G) to derive the estimation strategy. However, in the simulations, its influence will be considered and investigated in detail.

Furthermore, we assume that the incoupling losses before the amplification (mainly due to imperfect visibility and optical losses) can be characterized by the transmissivity η_{in} and an added zero-mean Gaussian noise ε_{in} :

$$X = \sqrt{\eta_{\text{in}}}x_{\text{in}} + \varepsilon_{\text{in}}, \quad (2)$$

where ε_{in} is normally distributed with zero mean and standard deviation δ_{in} .

From (1) and (2), we can estimate the initial quadrature variable x_{in} as

$$\hat{x}_{\text{in}} := \pm \sqrt{2N_{x^2} / (e^{2G}\eta_{\text{in}}\eta_{\text{out}})} - d / (e^G \sqrt{\eta_{\text{in}}}), \quad (3)$$

where $N_{x^2} = i_{x^2} - \langle \xi_{\text{det}} \rangle$ is the normalized and bias-corrected photocurrent. This estimator works well when the approximation in (1) is applicable (i.e. $e^{-G}P$ should be negligible compared to $e^G X + d$), which is true for the experiment in [40]. Also note that due to the subtraction, for really small values of i_{x^2} , the quantity below the square root can be negative. This can be handled technically, but it is not of large relevance for experiments similar to [40] as these data points do not contain much information anyway (they are dominated by detection noise) and become a non-issue for larger values of the displacement d .

More importantly, the two solutions (\pm) in the expression are not distinguishable. Therefore, we will investigate ways to advance this basic idea and thereby significantly extend the applicability and improve the efficiency of OPA tomography. We also explore the scenario when the intensity detector is exchanged for homodyne detection [33].

The original approach in [40] consisted of preparing a histogram of the measured photon numbers, and assuming that the distribution of the X quadrature is symmetric about the origin, and (3) allowed reconstructing the histogram of $|X|$. Albeit straightforward, there are a few problems with this method:

- (i) The bin widths of the reconstructed histogram are uneven: narrow for large values while very large for low values. This is because the estimation is based on constructing the histogram of intensities, which are non-linear in the quadrature.
- (ii) The precision of the estimator is worse for low values of x_{in} due to the relatively strong distortion effect of the detector noise ξ_{det} for small values (figure 2).
- (iii) The method only provides the statistics of $|X|$, and therefore, asymmetric input states cannot be estimated.

Provided G is large enough, these issues are mitigated—at least partially. Also, to an extent (see figure 2), by using large enough bins, the errors around zero might disappear (the positive and negative deviations are included in a single bin). However, it might be difficult in practice to achieve a high level of amplification without adding considerable extra noise to the signal. Also, this does not solve the issue of asymmetric input states. Moreover, many non-Gaussian states can have interesting nonclassical sub-Planck structures at the origin, as it is for amplitude or phase-diffused states [15, 54] and Fock and cat states [58–63].

Figure 2. The probability distribution of a Gaussian state (orange line) compared to the estimate obtained by the standard method using different parameters. The estimates are using different amplifications: $G = 4$ (black line), $G = 5$ (green line), $G = 6$ (brown line). The precision is improved by increasing the OPA amplification; still, in the plotted typical regime of parameters, all estimators have a problem in the vicinity of zero, which is critical for quantum non-Gaussian states. Simulation parameters can be found at the beginning of section 3.

To improve the method, we suggest the following changes:

Consistent binning The first issue is that instead of making a linear binning on the measurement outcome, we first do the transformation back to the quadrature x_{in} and only then define linear bins on that scale. With this, we can have a consistent binning with a fixed predefined resolution, which ensures that we obtain an evenly spaced estimate of the whole probability distribution.

Displacing the input An efficient way to avoid problems with low-intensity values is displacing the input state. This technique is broadly exploited in quantum optics, even for quantum non-Gaussian states like Fock states and their superpositions [25, 64, 65]. Technically, the most straightforward way of performing the displacement is adding a coherent source with a very asymmetrical beam splitter to the signal, for example, implemented for non-Gaussian states in [25]. Note that this approach is similar to unbalanced homodyning [66, 67], but they are not equivalent either technically or mathematically.

We estimate this shifted distribution, and at the end, we apply an inverse displacement to obtain the original distribution. This approach significantly reduces the distorting effect of post-amplification noises ϵ_{out} and ξ_{det} on the histograms. Note that besides reducing the effects of post-amplification noise, this technique can compensate for a limited value of G : with the added displacement, the amplified quadrature X is even more dominant over P .

Reconstructing asymmetric distributions We can use the displacement of input states to reconstruct asymmetric distributions. If the displacement is large enough, the support of the amplified quadrature is shifted wholly to the positive half-line, that is, one does not need to bother with the negative sign in (3).

It is also possible to solve the problem for smaller displacements: one needs to repeat the experiment with at least two different values of the displacement d and, from the resulting histograms, reconstruct the initial state's quadrature distribution by solving a simple least squares problem (for more details, see appendix A).

3. Numerical estimation from intensity detection

In the following, we will investigate the estimation properties for a set of input states by generating samples of N independent measurements and then applying the estimator to each sample. If not noted otherwise, we use the system parameters: $G = 4$, $\delta G = 0.01$, $\eta_{in} = 0.95$, $\delta_{in} = 1 - \eta_{in}$, $\eta_{out} = 0.1$, $\delta_{out} = 1 - \eta_{out}$, $\langle \xi_{det} \rangle = 2$, which corresponds to a realistic, stable setup. We use a $w = 0.05$ bin width and a sample size of $N = 10^5$ for histograms. Note that for realistic systems, N could be lower: if this is the case, one should use fewer bins (larger bin width w), but for this manuscript, we use these numbers to obtain more detailed graphs. Throughout the paper, we focus on the quality of histogram estimates; the Wigner functions of the different examined states are shown in appendix B.

We use fidelity as a figure of merit to compare the estimated histogram with the true input distribution. More specifically, we have to compare discretized classical probability distributions. So if we have reconstructed a histogram with relative frequency ν_i in bin i , and the theoretical distribution yields p_i for the

Figure 3. Estimation of squeezed states. Left column: a non-displaced squeezed state; Right column: a displaced squeezed state (squeezing parameter $g = -1 \Leftrightarrow 0.37$ squeezing factor, displacement 0.2). Top row: comparison of reconstructed histograms (dashed black line: original method, blue solid line: displaced approach) with the input distribution (orange line). Bottom row: Infidelity $1 - F$ as a function of the displacement d . The dashed purple line corresponds to the standard method with $\eta_{in} = 1$; the light blue, blue, and purple lines to the improved method with $\eta_{in} = 0.95, 0.99$, and 1, respectively.

same bin, then the fidelity is defined as

$$F = \left(\sum_i \sqrt{v_i \cdot p_i} \right)^2. \quad (4)$$

This quantity is between zero and one, with one corresponding to perfect overlap. Note that in our figures, we work with the equivalent quantity $1 - F$ called infidelity, which can be considered a badness of fit metric. This is because, otherwise, we would not be able to use a doubly logarithmic scale.

The probabilities p_i can be determined using the cumulative distribution function H of x_{in} :

$$p_i = H(x_i + w/2) - H(x_i - w/2),$$

with x_i denoting the center of bin i . If w is small enough, of course, $p_i \approx h(x_i) \cdot w$, with h denoting the probability density function of the input.

3.1. Estimation of squeezed coherent states

First, let us check the estimation of a non-displaced squeezed state (figure 3(a)). We can see that even with imperfections present, we can estimate the original distribution with high precision using our method. The standard method [40] has similar properties, except for some problems about zero, where detector noise distorts the outcome of the estimation.

Comparing the infidelities of the two estimation approaches (figure 3(c)), we see improvement even if we compare the lossless case using the standard method (purple dashed line) to the $\eta_{in} = 0.95$ case using the newly proposed approach (light blue solid line). The figure does not display lossy cases for the standard method as its performance does not significantly change as a result (see figure A2(b)). Note that considering Gaussian states, this is the ideal input for the original method, as it is symmetric and is not strongly squeezed (it is not strongly concentrated about zero).

That is, adding a displacement can significantly improve the quality of our estimation. This improvement is present for a wide range of displacement values (we should displace the whole distribution to the positive side). For smaller values of d , we need to apply the sophisticated method described in appendix A to reconstruct the input state adequately. This method has a slightly worse performance than the single displacement method used for large d ; nevertheless, it still outperforms the standard method. For larger displacements, the infidelity curve becomes essentially flat. The reason for this is clear: if the displaced state's support is already almost entirely on the positive half-line, displacing it further has only an infinitesimal benefit, which is overcome by finite-size effects (due to finite sample size in the simulation; this also holds in

Figure 4. Estimation of mixtures of squeezed states. Left column: a symmetric non-Gaussian state: a 50%–50% mixture of two non-displaced squeezed states ($g_A = -2$ and $g_B = -1 \Leftrightarrow$ squeezing factors 0.135 and 0.37); right column: an asymmetric non-Gaussian state the same mixture with displacement values of 0.2 and -0.2 , respectively. Top row: comparison of reconstructed histograms (dashed black line: original method, blue solid line: displaced approach) with the input distribution (orange line). Bottom row: infidelity $1 - F$ as a function of the displacement d . The dashed purple line corresponds to the standard method with $\eta_{in} = 1$; the light blue, blue, and purple lines to the improved method with $\eta_{in} = 0.95, 0.99$, and 1, respectively.

an experimental setting). These finite-size effects cause the fluctuations in the infidelity values in figure 3(c), but since the figure is logarithmic, they are best visible for the lowest values (purple line, $\eta_{in} = 1$). These observations hold for all examined input states.

If we displace the input squeezed state, the situation remains similar (figure 3(b)). The main difference is that the standard method becomes even less efficient. This is not surprising, as even a small displacement will break the needed symmetry for that method, i.e. the asymmetry causes further errors (see figure 3(b)). In contrast, our method is not sensitive to displacement (figure 3(d)); therefore, we can obtain similar efficiencies as in the symmetric case. More precisely, the displacement in the input state acts similarly to our additional displacement, so the original displacement will increase the efficiency for low displacement values d (i.e. the corresponding graphs are shifted a bit left compared to the non-displaced version).

3.2. Estimation of non-Gaussian states

In the following, we consider statistical mixtures of squeezed coherent states. They are non-Gaussian, so for example, we cannot reconstruct the input distribution from its variance; therefore, a full tomography is necessary in all cases.

If we check the histogram of the non-displaced mixture case (figure 4(a)), the main difference compared to the simple squeezed state is that the more squeezed ($g_A = 2$) component adds a larger peak about zero. Again, this reduces the efficiency of the standard method (figure 4(c) dashed black lines) since there are more observations close to zero, which are strongly affected by noise. Our method behaves similarly to the squeezed coherent state case (figure 3): the errors are somewhat larger, especially for the noisier case, since adding noise to a more squeezed state produces a larger change in its distribution.

We also examine a mixture of displaced squeezed states (figure 4(b)). This distribution is problematic for the standard method both regarding asymmetry and the detector noise around zero. Despite these issues, the infidelity of the standard approach is similar to the previous symmetric case. Even so, its lossless infidelity (purple dashed line is figure 4(d)) is only comparable to our method for the case of noisy input states ($\eta_{in} = 0.95$).

3.3. Estimation of cat states

After the mixture of squeezed coherent states examined in the previous section, we will now look at the superposition of two opposite coherent states, an even cat state $\propto |\alpha\rangle + |-\alpha\rangle$. In the following, we estimate the marginal distribution along both the long (figure 5(a)) and short (figure 5(b)) axis.

Figure 5. Estimation of cat state $\propto |\alpha\rangle + |-\alpha\rangle$ with $\alpha = 3$. Left column: position quadrature distribution; right column: momentum quadrature distribution. Top row: comparison of reconstructed histograms (dashed black line: original method, blue solid line: displaced approach) with the input distribution (orange line). Bottom row: $1 - F$ of the quadrature distributions as a function of the displacement d , where F is defined by (4). The dashed lines correspond to the standard method; the solid lines correspond to our improved method; the light blue, blue, and purple lines with $\eta_{\text{in}} = 0.95, 0.99$, and 1 , respectively.

The estimation in the position quadrature (where the superposed coherent states are located) works reasonably well for the standard method, the improvement from the new scheme is about two-fold for all examined values of η_{in} (see figure 5(c) solid vs. dashed lines). The reason for this limited difference is that its density around zero is quite small, so the error caused by detection noise is also minimal, meaning that both our method and standard method accurately estimate the distribution.

On the other hand, the estimation in the momentum quadrature (where the interference fringe and sub-Planck structure from the superposed coherent states rises, figure 5(b)) has a quite similar advantage of our method in the origin as in the case of non-displaced squeezed states, due to the similarity of their distributions around zero. This similarity results in similar estimation performance (figure 5(d)); that is, we get a limited improvement for the noisy case and up to two orders of magnitude improvement in the ideal case.

3.4. Estimation of Fock states

Finally, we examine different Fock states. These are symmetric non-Gaussian states which have a negative Wigner function. Similarly to the previously discussed states, we only look at the marginal distribution of the amplified quadrature x (for further details regarding the simulation, see appendix C).

By checking the histogram of the single-photon case (figure 6(a)), we can see that this is a case that can be estimated very efficiently, even with the standard method. The reason is simple: this state is symmetric, and its density around zero is negligible, so the observed errors around very low photon numbers are insignificant. This high efficiency of the standard method is also apparent in figure 6(c) (dashed lines). We can obtain only a small improvement in the lossy cases. Therefore, the single-photon state is the ideal testbed for the standard method to reconstruct the initial distribution.

Examining the two-photon state (figure 6(b)), the significance of the peak in zero is quite apparent: the standard method performs much worse (dashed lines) than in the single-photon case, whereas the newly proposed approach provides similar results. The overall behavior is also quite similar to the short axis of the cat state examined in figure 5(d).

Note also that the obtained efficiency is very high in either case: we can estimate Fock states much more precisely than the different squeezed states. The reason for this is simple: the distribution of these states is less concentrated about the origin, so we amplify much larger values, and the estimation is better for larger photon numbers.

Figure 6. Estimation of Fock states. Left column: single-photon state; right column: two-photon state. Top row: comparison of reconstructed histograms (dashed black line: original method, blue solid line: displaced approach) with the input distribution (orange line). Bottom row: $1 - F$ as a function of the displacement d . The dashed lines correspond to the standard method, the solid lines correspond to our improved method; the light blue, blue, and purple lines with $\eta_{in} = 0.95, 0.99$, and 1 , respectively.

4. Dependence on amplification

As suggested earlier, one of the key factors in estimation efficiency is the squeezing parameter G , so in the following, we will investigate its effect. Note that the relative variance amplification is e^{2G} , so the amplification in decibels is proportional to G ($G \cdot 20 \log_{10} e$); so, for example, $G = 4$ is equivalent to about 35 dB of anti-squeezing. Importantly, such high levels of amplification are experimentally feasible [40, 68, 69]. Since they are equivalent, we use the terms amplification and squeezing parameter interchangeably throughout the paper.

Firstly, for non-displaced squeezed state inputs (figure 7(a), green lines), we observe that both our method (solid) and the standard method (dashed) saturate at the same low level of error. However, there is a significant difference in where those methods achieve these saturated values: the standard method needs at least $G = 5$, while our method achieves similar performance already at $G \approx 3$. So using our method, much lower amplification suffices to achieve optimal performance, which might be useful in practical applications.

On the other hand, the difference is even more significant for the displaced squeezed state (figure 7(a), pink lines). Our method (solid) has the same efficiency as before, as the method is not sensitive to displacement. In contrast, the original method cannot handle asymmetric states, so it saturates at a significantly higher level of infidelity, which spoils the estimate (see also figure 3(b)).

We can come to similar conclusions considering mixtures of squeezed states (figure 7(b)). For the symmetric scenario (green lines), the estimates have the same properties as before. The only difference is that the saturated level of error is a little higher (0.04 vs 0.013), which is caused by the bigger bias of the larger squeezing (adding a fixed amount of noise to a larger squeezing causes a larger change in the probability distribution). In the asymmetric case, where both components in the mixture are displaced (figure 4(d)), the infidelity of either method increases. But again, our method saturates already at a low level of amplification ($G \approx 3$). This is remarkable as one of the peaks in the distribution has a squeezing parameter of $g_A = 2$ (instead of $g_A = 1$), and a similar amplification is sufficient to achieve optimal performance. Again, the standard method saturates at a higher level as it cannot handle asymmetric distributions.

Regarding cat states, we see that the achievable accuracy is mostly determined by the input quadrature's density in the vicinity of the origin. The quadrature probability density function (PDF) along the long axis is very well separated from the origin, the probability of low quadratures is very small, therefore the measurement is much less influenced by detection noise. Whereas along the short axis, most of the weight is close to zero, and therefore detection noise has a more pronounced effect.

Finally, for Fock states (figure 7(d)), the situation is similar to the other symmetric cases: our method and the standard method converge to the same values in both the Fock-1 (green) and Fock-2 (pink) cases.

Again, our method works better for lower values of G , which is more prominent for the Fock-2 state. The obtained optimal infidelity is unsurprisingly somewhat higher for the Fock-2 state, but even there, estimation efficiency is better than in any of the previously discussed squeezed cases.

Of course, the quality of the estimation depends on the other parameters of the system as well. We checked the robustness of our method (for more details, see appendix D), and we can conclude that if the various imperfections are below a threshold, we can achieve similar fidelities, and the proposed method efficiently reconstructs the unknown state. While above that threshold, the estimate deteriorates rapidly.

The pre-amplification noise (ε_{in}) is the most significant of the different types of imperfections. This is because, in realistic scenarios, that is the only case where we cannot easily get below the critical threshold. This is problematic because the added noise is amplified together with the signal, causing a significant bias in our estimation. And this problem cannot be easily circumvented by other improvements (e.g. by increasing the value of G). Knowing the variance of the pre-amplification noise, one can try to deconvolute this added Gaussian noise ε_{in} from the estimated histogram of the quadrature x_{in} . However, considering that one ultimately also wants to reconstruct not only a histogram but the whole Wigner function, that would be combining two ill-posed problems: deconvolution and inverse Radon transform.

5. Comparison with homodyne detection

In the following, we will compare the previously discussed intensity-based tomography to OPA-assisted homodyne detection [22, 37]. In other words, the detector in figure 1 stands for using a local oscillator to obtain the quadrature in a specific direction (instead of an intensity detector). If we again do the amplification in direction x , we can observe the photocurrent difference:

$$i_x = [\sqrt{\eta_{\text{out}}} (e^G \cdot X + d) + \varepsilon_{\text{out}}] \cdot \alpha_{\text{LO}} + \xi_{\text{det}}. \quad (5)$$

where i_x is normalized to shot noise units of the actual quadrature of light, α_{LO} is the strength of the local oscillator, and as before, we have

$$X = \sqrt{\eta_{\text{in}}} x_{\text{in}} + \varepsilon_{\text{in}}. \quad (6)$$

The post-amplification losses and noises can have multiple sources. For the sake of simplicity, we will only use in our simulation the dominant parts: we will assume that loss is caused by the detection efficiency ($\eta_{\text{out}} = \eta_{\text{det}}$), while the noise is due to imperfect detection ($\delta_{\text{out}} = \sqrt{1 - \eta_{\text{det}}} \cdot \delta_0$) and electronic noise (ξ_{det}) contributing to the photocurrent i_x .

Figure 8. Infidelity of the homodyne detection protocol as a function of the OPA amplification G . We plotted lines for $\eta_{\text{out}} = 1$ (black), $\eta_{\text{out}} = 0.9$ (red), $\eta_{\text{out}} = 0.5$ (orange), and $\eta_{\text{out}} = 0.1$ (yellow). For comparison, we plotted the standard OPA method (green dotted) and our improved OPA method (green dashed) for $\eta_{\text{out}} = 0.1$. We have $\alpha_{\text{LO}} = 10^5$ and $\langle \xi_{\text{det}} \rangle = 10^3$, otherwise the same parameters as in figure 3.

For the case of homodyne detection (5), the situation is much simpler as the output is a linear function of the input state (instead of quadratic). So here, we can simply obtain an unbiased estimator:

$$\hat{x}_{\text{in}} := N_x / (e^G \alpha_{\text{LO}} \sqrt{\eta_{\text{in}} \eta_{\text{out}}}) - d / (e^G \sqrt{\eta_{\text{in}}}), \quad (7)$$

with the properly normalized photocurrent: $N_x = i_x - \langle \xi_{\text{det}} \rangle$ after we subtract the mean detector noise causing unwanted bias.

If we compare homodyne estimation with different detector efficiencies (figure 8, solid lines), we can conclude that they behave quite similarly. If the OPA gain G is large enough, one can obtain optimal performance. Below this threshold, the estimation deteriorates. This decrease in performance is more prominent for lower detector efficiencies, but only for relatively low OPA gains. If the OPA gain is large enough, we get similar estimation performance independently of the detector efficiency.

If we compare this protocol with our method (figure 8, yellow vs. green dashed line), we can see that they have the same efficiency. The only difference is that in the case of intensity detection, an added displacement was needed for the insensitivity of the scheme around zero, which is not an issue for homodyne detection. It is important to note that the same performance is only true if both methods have the same losses and noises, which is not true in practice (intensity detection and homodyne measurement are working with fundamentally different parameters). Therefore, the applicability of the different detection schemes mainly depends on the physical specification of the setup; e.g. for a heavily multimode source, the phase matching with the local oscillator could be more problematic.

6. Distillable squeezing

We will demonstrate the power of this newly proposed method by using the resulting histograms to uncover sub-Planck structures [14] by estimating distillable squeezing [55]. The squeezing below the vacuum state distillable from non-Gaussian quadrature distribution is sufficient to find and conclusively measure sub-Planck structures in that quadrature. It is an operational witness that the original state had some non-classical change in phase space faster than classical states, even though the variance in that non-Gaussian distribution might be larger than the vacuum state variance.

For example, the cat-like superpositions of two real-valued coherent states that are different in position analyzed in the text will have sub-Planck narrowing in the center of interference fringes in the momentum. The momentum distribution can be distilled into a Gaussian squeezing corresponding to a large local curvature around the global maximum of momentum distribution in the origin. For such cat states, such sub-Planck structure is present only in one of two-phase space variables. Distillable squeezing is, therefore, sufficient to capture sub-Planck structures of non-Gaussian states in one variable.

On the other hand, for a single photon state (and generally Fock states), such a sub-Planck structure can be witnessed by distillable squeezing in any quadrature variable due to the phase-insensitive nature of Fock states. Therefore, by changing the phase of the OPA pump and displacement, we can reliably measure and estimate different quadratures using our techniques and confirm the sub-Planck structures, thereby obtaining an estimate of the distillable squeezing below the vacuum state. It will confirm that the sub-Planck structure is phase-insensitive and simultaneously present in any quadrature of the Fock states.

For a Gaussian state, the level of squeezing can be determined from the value of the variance in the squeezed direction. For non-Gaussian states, one can estimate distillable squeezing from the maximal

curvature of the probability density function [55]. For Gaussian states, the two definitions are, of course, equivalent. However, the latter can be applied to our other investigated non-Gaussian states as well.

Note that due to its local nature, the second definition requires the estimated histogram to be quite precise, which is why the standard method is not applicable due to its inaccuracy in the vicinity of zero (and its restriction to symmetrical states). In other words, if the maximum under consideration happens to be located at zero, estimating distillable squeezing becomes impractical.

We used a very simple method to obtain the maximal curvature: we checked our histogram for local maxima and estimated the curvature in each. We calculated the curvature for any given maximum by fitting a parabola to a certain number of bins m symmetrically around the maximum. We chose this method for curvature estimation because it is quite straightforward; one can find this and further similar approaches in [70]. If the fitted parabola has a formula of $\ln[p(x)] = -a(x-b)^2 + c$, then according to [55], the distillable variance is

$$V_d = \frac{p(b)}{|p''(b)|} = \frac{1}{|\ln p(x)|''_{x=b}} = 1/2a. \quad (8)$$

Note that the squeezing parameter can be obtained from this quantity as $g = 1/2 \ln(2V_d)$. Naturally, as a parabola has three parameters, this fit requires at least three points (including the bin with maximal value). If we increase the number of bins, we will get a wider interval where we perform the fit (including more data points).

Figure 9 shows the distillable variance from our estimated histograms (note that with the used convention, vacuum quadrature variance is $1/2$). Knowing the value of the input transmissivity (η_{in}), we can calculate the level of squeezing after adding this noise (blue vs. purple dashed lines) due to the additivity of the variances. Note that removing the added Gaussian noise from the histogram is not this straightforward (it would require deconvolution). Conversely, using this equivalence, if we have a precise value for the distillable variance for the lossy case (blue solid lines), then from that, we can simply obtain a precise estimate of the actual value of the squeezing (purple solid lines). The thick yellow lines show the values calculated from the noiseless (ideal) theoretical histograms.

Ideally, our method (solid lines) should be close to the actual values of squeezing (dashed line). Our method to estimate the distillable variance performs slightly worse, but in all cases, the difference is small, meaning we can estimate the squeezing relatively precisely. One can see that in all cases if we use a higher number of bins m , our estimation becomes somewhat worse. This worsening happens because the curvature is a local property, so adding more points decreases the estimation's accuracy. However, according to our

experience, adding 1-2 extra data points can help negate the statistical fluctuations of individual data points, compensating for the negative effect of including farther-off points in the estimation.

If we check the estimation of the squeezing parameter for squeezed states (left column), we can see no significant difference between the displaced and non-displaced cases. This is expected as our method is not sensitive to displacement: one only has to find the maximum of the histogram and fit a parabola. A similar conclusion is true for the mixture of squeezed states (middle column), where, unsurprisingly, our estimate is less accurate. But we could clearly see that our estimated levels of squeezing are lower than in the previous case, so with this method, we can estimate the more squeezed ($g_A = 2$) part of the distribution (which would not be possible if we used the variance, which is determined mainly by the less squeezed state $g_B = 1$). Also, it is interesting that if the two distributions are separated by displacements (figure 9(d)), the accuracy does not improve compared to the case of overlapping non-displaced distributions (figure 9(c)).

Finally, we investigated the distillable variance for the even cat state and the Fock-2 state (right column). Note that in these cases, using the method described in [55], we can approximate a squeezed state around zero using multiple copies of the given non-Gaussian states. Here, the variance of the distribution is not useful for this purpose at all, so the only viable method to obtain the distillable squeezing is via estimating the curvature from the estimated distribution (histogram). We can see that the obtained squeezing is less stable numerically than for Gaussian states. For Gaussian states, $\ln p(x)$ is exactly a parabola, but this is not true for non-Gaussian states (figures 9(c)–(f)). Therefore, the curvature estimation gets more biased by including more points about the maximum (see also appendix C.4). We emphasize here that the value our procedure provides is an estimate of and not an upper bound on distillable squeezing. That is, the sign of the bias depends on the specific state we examine: the peaks of the cat and Fock-2 states happen to be narrower than suggested by their curvature in the maximum, while the peak for the mixture of squeezed states is wider. One can infer the sign of the bias from the trend of the estimate when including more points.

In conclusion, there is a trade-off when selecting the optimal number of bins. Including somewhat more bins makes the estimation more numerically stable, but at the cost of an increased bias (at least in the general, non-Gaussian case). In order to keep this unwanted bias minimal, we should take fewer bins (at most 4–5 bins) for our estimation. Note that we can improve the situation by performing longer measurements which results in bins with more points, that is, a more stable PDF estimate. In the asymptotic limit (if binning is unchanged), the purple solid lines in figure 9 converge to the yellow ones, and choosing $m = 3$ is best.

7. Conclusion and discussion

We proposed an improved method for OPA tomography that is applicable directly to non-Gaussian states of light. The improvement's essential element is adding a displacement step post-amplification to the standard scheme proposed in [40]. The displacement significantly increases the accuracy around zero, as without it, there is a blind spot that distorts the whole distribution. This effect is quite apparent for the distillation of squeezing, where—if the origin is the most likely value of the investigated quadrature—the histogram yielded by the original method becomes useless.

We examined the performance of both the single- and the multiple-displacement versions of the proposed method on a number of input states numerically. Considering the simpler, single-displacement scenario in an experimental setting, one does not know beforehand if the applied displacement is large enough to entirely shift the support of the quadrature to the positive half-line. To remedy this, one could first perform the measurement without displacement and, from that, estimate the maximum of the absolute value of the quadrature in question. Applying a displacement larger than this value is sufficient for the single-displacement method to be applicable. If this displacement is not experimentally feasible, the multiple-displacement approach discussed in appendix A is still applicable.

Compared to the standard method, we can significantly improve the estimation efficiency given a fixed level of OPA amplification G (figures 3–6). More importantly, our method does not assume that the input state is symmetric, so the range of applications is much broader. Furthermore, even for states symmetric about the origin, we could obtain an order of magnitude lower infidelity using fewer assumptions. Note that this improvement is attainable using a relatively small displacement already, comparable to the mean magnitude of the quadrature (as opposed to the local oscillator in the homodyne scheme). Fock states present a special case of symmetric quantum non-Gaussian states. For Fock states, the improved method is even more precise than for Gaussian states. Note that for odd Fock states, this precision is also approachable by the standard approach since the quadrature distribution has a zero in the origin for such states.

The efficiency of our improved method saturates at a relatively low level of OPA amplification (figure 7), i.e. it is not necessary to have a very strong OPA (which could be challenging to achieve without increasing the noise level) to perform an efficient estimation. We also investigated the effects of different imperfections and concluded that our method is relatively robust against them. Comparing our method to homodyne

detection with a pre-amplification step (that is, exchanging the photodetector for homodyning in the original scheme), we see that they have the same efficiency (figure 8). For our OPA tomography, we need to apply a displacement to achieve this optimal performance, which is replaced by using a local oscillator in the homodyning case. Finally, we investigated the precision of the estimation of distillable squeezing for different Gaussian and non-Gaussian states (figure 9). We could use our high-precision OPA histograms to estimate the curvature of the probability density function about zero, which would not be feasible without the extension introduced in the current manuscript.

An important note is that in our scheme (figure 1), we used the displacement as part of the measurement setup, i.e. post-amplification. This was done because usually, in a heavily multimode scenario, applying a displacement causes significant loss, which can be easily dealt with if the loss happens after the amplification. However, if the displacement could be performed close to ideally (without causing much loss or noise), then it could be performed instead before the amplification, meaning that a minimal level of displacement could achieve optimal performance. Also, note that even though applying a displacement is fundamentally a similar concept to homodyning, technically, it is still very different as we apply orders of magnitude weaker displacement compared to the case of a local oscillator.

Overall, we achieved a significant improvement in both the applicability and the performance of OPA tomography. Our improved tomography method is feasible with a general input state (it could be asymmetrical, non-Gaussian, or both), a lower strength of OPA amplification is necessary for optimal performance, and even with having more losses, it is comparable with its alternative of using homodyne detection with pre-amplification. Our results will inspire the field, and OPA amplification will prove to be an excellent alternative to classical estimation approaches in many different scenarios involving multimode and large telecom bandwidth states of light. Moreover, such a method can find applications to detect and identify quantum non-Gaussian states of other mechanical and atomic systems, like single-phonon states quantum optomechanics [71, 72] and optically controlled atomic ensembles [73, 74].

Data availability statement

All data that support the findings of this study are included within the article (and any supplementary files).

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Appendix A. Estimation with multiple displacements

We propose a scheme that is composed of two different approaches: a simple and an advanced one, which relies on a linear least squares problem. In this section, we omit the details of the scheme and only focus on estimating the PDF $f(x)$ of a random variable X based on one or more samples $\mathbf{y} = \{y_i = |x_i + d|\}_{i=1, \dots, n}$.

If the displacement is large enough so that $\forall i : x_i + d > 0$, there is no need to have more samples with different displacements: $x_i = y_i - d$, and one can simply construct a histogram from these values. However, one does not necessarily know beforehand what value of d is sufficient for that. Therefore, applying a second displacement d' slightly larger than the first is advisable. If the shape of the histogram of y' is just a shifted version of the histogram of y , we can be sure that even the initial displacement d was large enough to shift the support of f to the positive half-line, and both samples y and y' can be used to estimate the initial distribution.

If, however, the shapes of the histograms of y and y' do not coincide, one can still use two samples to reconstruct the initial distribution f .

For the sake of simplicity, we describe the algorithm for the first displacement $d = 0$, but it works much the same for $d \neq 0$. First, we perform two measurements, with $N/2$ observations each:

- non-displaced sample: $\{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_{N/2}\}; y_i = \sqrt{x_i^2}$; the PDF of Y is $g(y) = f(y) + f(-y)$;

Figure A1. Reconstruction of asymmetric probability distributions. (a) Histogram of the absolute values (the negative and positive values cannot be discriminated) for the original and displaced distribution, (b) the reconstructed histogram (dark blue points) with the baseline of the original distribution (light blue line). The underlying distribution was a 50–50 mixture of two Gaussians, the first centered at -1 , with a standard deviation of 0.4 , and the second centered at 1 , with a standard deviation of 0.6 . The sample sizes were $n = 10^5$, the value of the displacement was $d = 0.6$, the resolution used for binning was $w = 0.2$.

- displaced sample: $\{z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{N/2}\}; z_i = \sqrt{(x'_i + d')^2}$; the PDF of Z is $h(y) = f(y - d') + f(-y - d')$.

Then, we calculate the histograms of the two samples using the same binning, with bin centers in $\frac{w}{2}, \frac{3w}{2}, \dots, (n - \frac{1}{2})w$; with n_1 denoting the last non-empty bin for the y -sample, and n_2 denoting the last non-empty bin in the displaced sample:

- $\mathbf{g} \equiv (g_1, g_2, \dots, g_{n_1})^\top$
- $\mathbf{h} \equiv (h_1, h_2, \dots, h_{n_2})^\top$

These histograms are shown in figure A1(a).

Let us assume that $n_1 \leq n_2$, then we can estimate $\left\{ f\left(-n_1 + \frac{1}{2}\right)w, \dots, f\left(-\frac{w}{2}\right), f\left(\frac{w}{2}\right), \dots, f\left(n_1 - \frac{1}{2}\right)w \right\}$, we denote these points by the vector $\mathbf{f} \equiv (f_1, f_2, \dots, f_{2n_1})^\top$.

Using these notations, we have the matrix equation

$$\begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{A} \\ \mathbf{B} \end{pmatrix} \cdot \mathbf{f} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{g} \\ \mathbf{h} \end{pmatrix},$$

with $A_{ij} = \delta_{j, n_1 + 1 - i} + \delta_{j, n_1 + i}$, $i = 1, \dots, n_1, j = 1, \dots, 2n_1$; and $B_{ij} = \delta_{j, n_1 - \Delta n + i} + \delta_{j, n_1 + 1 - \Delta n - i}$, $\Delta n = n_2 - n_1$, $i = 1, \dots, n_2, j = 1, \dots, 2n_1$; with $\delta_{i,j}$ denoting the Kronecker delta symbol.

That is, we have $2n_1$ unknowns and $2n_1 + \Delta n$ equations, which is overdetermined. Due to the randomness of the histogram, however, the best solution is not discarding Δn of these, but rather solve the equation in the least squares sense:

$$\hat{\mathbf{f}} = \underset{\mathbf{f}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \left\| \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{A} \\ \mathbf{B} \end{pmatrix} \cdot \mathbf{f} - \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{g} \\ \mathbf{h} \end{pmatrix} \right\|^2,$$

The result of this minimization along with the true PDF $f(x)$ is shown in figure A1(b). Note that even though the procedure can be refined by taking into account the errors of \mathbf{g} and \mathbf{h} , that is, by solving a weighted least

squares problem, we have found that this does not result in any improvement. Constraining the minimization to $f_i > 0$, however, visibly improves the PDF-estimates. On the other hand, for $n_1 > n_2$, by defining $\tilde{X} \equiv -X - d$, we arrive at the previous case, that is, we can estimate $\tilde{f}(x)$, from which it is easy to calculate $f(x)$.

For our figures, we refined this basic idea of least-squares minimization by applying three displacements instead of two. This was done so that we might discard equations corresponding to low intensities because those were highly affected by detection noise. We also smoothed the result by a simple moving average algorithm.

We show the features of this method in action for squeezed vacuum in figure A2. If the displacement d is too small to bring the whole distribution to the positive half-line, then the simple algorithm cannot handle the situation properly (see figure A2(a), blue solid line). This is also apparent in the right-hand figure: the infidelity of the simple method increases for low values of d . We can fix this by using multiple small displacements (both in the positive and negative directions) to obtain a decent estimate of the unknown distribution (see figure A2(a), blue dashed line, and figure A2(b) thick solid lines). The performance for $\eta_{\text{in}} = 0.95$ is mainly dominated by the bias caused by loss, while in the other two cases, the error is dominated by the numerical errors of the sophisticated method (which are about one order of magnitude larger than the errors for the simple method). Note that we also plotted here the errors of the standard method for three different values of η_{in} . These levels are close to each other because the errors are dominated by detector noise and not by losses. This is why we plotted only the $\eta_{\text{in}} = 0.95$ line for the standard method in the main text.

Appendix B. Investigated input states

The Wigner functions of the eight input states we considered in our simulations are shown in figure B1. Panels (a) through (f) correspond to states built from coherent states by squeezing, mixing, or superposing. Panels (g) and (h) show the Wigner functions of the single-photon and the two-photon states. Regarding each state, we examined the estimation of the distribution of the x quadrature.

Appendix C. Detailed analysis of Fock states

In this section, we look at the difference between a full Wigner function-based simulation of the experiment and only looking at the distribution of the square of the amplified quadrature. Due to its analytic tractability, we use a single photon state for demonstration. We can conclude that the two approaches produce very similar distributions, and we therefore used the simpler, quadrature-based approach to produce the figures in the main text. Also, we show that the efficient reconstruction of the marginals allows the reconstruction of the full Wigner tomography. Finally, we provide a more detailed analysis of the distilable squeezing as the Fock-state distribution is only locally similar to a Gaussian distribution around zero.

C.1. Simplified simulation method

Generally, knowing the Wigner function $W(x, p)$ of an arbitrary state, the probability of observing n photons can be calculated as

$$p_n = 2\pi \int W(x, p) W_n(x, p) dx dp, \tag{C.1}$$

with $W_n(x, p) \equiv \frac{(-1)^n}{\pi} e^{-p^2 - x^2} \mathcal{L}_n [2(p^2 + x^2)]$ denoting the Wigner function of the n^{th} Fock state;

$\mathcal{L}_n(t) \equiv \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \frac{(-1)^k}{k!} t^k$ denotes the n^{th} Laguerre polynomial. As previously, we use the convention $\hat{x} = (a^\dagger + a)/\sqrt{2}$, $\hat{p} = (a - a^\dagger)/i\sqrt{2}$, $[\hat{x}, \hat{p}] = i$. Calculating (C.1) numerically can be challenging, especially for large values of n , due to the oscillations in W_n . We will now show through the example of a single photon that, in our specific case, simulating the amplified quadrature suffices to sample the output intensity distribution.

Our aim is to determine the photon number distribution for light passing through an optical parametric amplifier (including realistic noises) for simulation purposes. The steps of the model under consideration are the following:

- (0) Input: $W_{\text{in}}(x, p)$
- (1) beam splitter: before amplification, with transmittance η_{in} (admixture of vacuum);

$$W_{(1)}(x, p) = \int dx' dp' W_{\text{in}}(x_{\text{in}}, p_{\text{in}}) W_0(x_0, p_0) \tag{C.2}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_{\text{in}} & p_{\text{in}} \\ x_0 & p_0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{\eta_{\text{in}}} & -\sqrt{1-\eta_{\text{in}}} \\ \sqrt{1-\eta_{\text{in}}} & \sqrt{\eta_{\text{in}}} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x & p \\ x' & p' \end{pmatrix}$$

- (2) parametric amplification of the x quadrature with gain G ;

$$W_{(2)}(x, p) = W_{(1)}(x \cdot e^{-G}, p \cdot e^G)$$

- (3) displacement with d along the x axis;

$$W_{(3)}(x, p) = W_{(2)}(x - d, p)$$

- (4) beam splitter: after amplification, with transmittance η_{out} , similarly to (C.2) $\rightarrow W_{(4)}(x, p)$;
- (5) detector: adds Poissonian noise with expectation λ ; the expectation of this noise is subtracted \rightarrow observable photon number probabilities p_n .

Steps 4 and 5 can be approximated by calculating the number distribution p_n from $W_{(3)}$ and rescaling that $n \rightarrow \eta_{\text{out}} \cdot n$, and adding a somewhat larger noise λ .

C.2. Comparison with analytic number distribution for zero displacement

The number distribution of a squeezed Fock state n [75] is

$$p_k = \frac{k!n!}{\cosh^{2n+1}(G)} \left(\frac{\tanh(G)}{2} \right)^{k-n} \times \left(\sum_{m=\max(0, \frac{n-k}{2})}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor} \frac{(-1)^m \left(\frac{\sinh(G)}{2} \right)^{2m}}{m!(n-2m)! \left(\frac{k-n}{2} + m \right)!} \right)^2 \tag{C.3}$$

if $n - k$ is even, zero otherwise. It is straightforward to show that for $n = 0$, that is, the number distribution of squeezed vacuum, $N_{0,G} \sim 2 \times U_1$, where U_1 has a negative binomial distribution with parameters $r = 1/2$ and $p = 1/\cosh^2 G$; whereas for $n = 1$, $N_{1,G} \sim 2 \times U_2 + 1$, where U_2 has a negative binomial distribution with parameters $r = 3/2$ and $p = 1/\cosh^2 G$.

Up to step 1, we either have a single photon that reaches the OPA with probability η_{in} and subsequently gets squeezed, or vacuum with probability $1 - \eta_{\text{in}}$. The resulting random variable after step 2 is, therefore, a probabilistic mixture of two negative binomial random variables:

$$N_{(2)} = \begin{cases} 2U_1 & \text{w. prob. } 1 - \eta_{\text{in}}, \\ 2U_2 + 1 & \text{w. prob. } \eta_{\text{in}}. \end{cases} \tag{C.4}$$

Applying the previously mentioned simplification and with $d = 0$, after step 5, we have $N_{(5)} = \eta_{\text{out}}N_{(2)} + U_3 - \lambda$, where U_3 is Poissonian with expectation λ . As it is simply based on sampling negative binomial and Poissonian distributions, it is quite easy to generate a sample of $N_{(5)}$.

As in the general case, it is non-trivial to calculate the number distribution, we look into how the distribution of $x^2/2$ compares to the number distribution in this simple case. The Wigner function and the PDF of x after step 2 and the PDF of $x^2/2$ derived from it can be given as

$$\begin{aligned}
 W_{(2)}(x, p) &= \frac{1}{\pi} e^{-e^{2G}p^2 - e^{-2G}x^2} [2\eta_{\text{in}}(e^{2G}p^2 + e^{-2G}x^2 - 1) + 1] \\
 \mathcal{P}_{(2)}(x) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} e^{-e^{-2G}x^2 - 3G} (2\eta_{\text{in}}x^2 + (1 - \eta_{\text{in}})e^{2G}) \\
 h_{(2)}(\nu) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\nu}} \left[\mathcal{P}_{(2)}(\sqrt{2\nu}) + \mathcal{P}_{(2)}(-\sqrt{2\nu}) \right] = \\
 &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\nu}} \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} e^{-2e^{-2G}\nu - 3G} (4\eta_{\text{in}}\nu + (1 - \eta_{\text{in}})e^{2G}).
 \end{aligned}$$

As the left part of figure C1 shows, the correspondence between the number distribution and the PDF of $x^2/2$ is quite good, except in the vicinity of zero, where $h_{(2)}$ diverges. However, even this difference is diminished after adding the noise in step 6, as the right part of the same figure shows.

In summary, the PDF of $x^2/2$ (figure C1) is an excellent approximation for the photon number PDF. For this specific input state, our simulations showed a very good agreement for $G > 1.5$, which is well below the experimental values used in [40].

C.3. Reconstruction of the Wigner function

Figure C2(b) shows the reconstruction of the Fock-2 Wigner function based on measurements in twenty evenly spaced directions. The algorithm used was the standard filtered back projection; we made no assumptions about the symmetry of the state.

C.4. Gaussian approximation for distillable squeezing

Figure C3 shows the behavior of curvature estimation for a non-Gaussian peak. Equation (8) for estimating the curvature is most stable for Gaussian peaks, that is, where the logarithm of the PDF is an upside-down parabola. The depicted peak of the Fock-2 state is narrower than its curvature in the maximum would imply for a Gaussian peak. Therefore, the estimated distillable variance decreases as one takes into account more and more points about the maximum.

Figure C2. Reconstruction of Fock-2 state. (a) Analytic Wigner function of input state. (b) Estimate based on 20 measurements in directions evenly spaced between 0 and 171 degrees.

Figure C3. Illustration of the curvature fit for the Fock-2 state using (a) 4 points and (b) 10 points. The orange line shows the quadrature distribution of the Fock-2 state near zero, the blue line shows which bins are used for the fit, and the black dashed line shows the fitted parabola.

Appendix D. Robustness analysis

Checking the robustness of our method (see figure D1), we can conclude that if the imperfections are not too large, we can achieve a similarly accurate tomography. We see quite similar behavior when looking at the fluctuations of different parameters: below a threshold, they do not affect the error of the estimated histogram, while beyond it, the error starts to increase rapidly. So, keeping these parameters below these threshold values, we have reasonable room for possible uncertainties where the algorithm efficiently reconstructs the state. Note that in our simulations, by default, we used the parameters: $\delta_{\text{in}} = 0.01$ or 0.05 (pre-amplification noise), $\delta_{\text{out}} = 0.9$ (post-amplification noise), $\delta G = 0.01$ (standard deviation of amplification strength), $\xi_{\text{det}} = 2$ (detector noise). These figures show that the default set of parameters is well within the safe zone. The only exception to this is the pre-amplification noise δ_{in} .

From a technical perspective, it is essential to minimize pre-amplification noises, as that is the only case where we cannot easily achieve the high-accuracy regime. Also, note that, in essence, our algorithm estimates the convolution of the pre-amplification noise and the actual state of interest. This noise is amplified to the same extent as the signal, so this problem cannot be circumvented by other improvements (e.g. by increasing the value of OPA amplification G). So when the value of δ_{in} is large, the estimated histogram will not have a small error. Knowing its value, it is possible to deconvolute it from the histogram. However, this is a separate task and does not work as well if the state is not close to Gaussian. Therefore, we have omitted the deconvolution problem from our discussions.

Another important observation is that the parameters of the system are strongly connected to the estimation performance. In figure D2, we show this effect by plotting the error as a function of post-amplification transmittance η_{out} . We can see that if we change the value of another parameter, there is always a visible change in the performance. Both in the case of detector noise ξ_{det} (left subfigure) and amplification G (right subfigure), the observed error is only different for relatively low values of the post-amplification transmittance. If the loss is low enough (i.e. the transmittance η_{out} is large), the error saturates at the same optimal level. This means that except for the pre-amplification noise, we can

compensate for all other imperfections by improving another parameter. In our example, to achieve optimal performance, we decreased the post-amplification loss sufficiently, but it works similarly for other parameters (like increasing the OPA amplification G).

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